

Guide for testing methodology

Historical and textual analysis

1. Legal action: considering the action recorded in the document, choose one of the following options:
 - Sale.
 - Will.
 - Grant/Donation.
 - Exchange.
 - Assets distribution agreement.
 - Agreement or dispute.
 - Charter of freedom.

2. Key features of the individual at the social level: Are roles or labels recognized, especially those that may identify the individual as having a high social status?
 - Patronymic: the individual(s) appear with an identifier (e.g. surname: Vimara **Pelaez**, Ildofensa **Vimaraz**...) next to the name. [Nicknames are not patronymic].
 - Social labels: the individual(s) appear with a special identifier regarding their social category, profession, status or activity (e.g. **don** Pelagius, **domna** Iberia, **comes** Petrus, **presbiter** Vimara, **abba** Iulianus, etc.). [*uxore* mea or widow are not type labels because they refer to a circumstantial situation which does not stand out in the community].
 - Prestigious assets: reference to properties of considerable value (e.g. large tracts of land, scattered properties, villas [covering a large area and perhaps including several houses, cultivation areas, etc.], saltworks, horses...).

3. Interaction individuals-juridical action
 - Are there vertical relationships between social groups of different status?
 - If so, could this interaction be identified as a part of a dependency relationship?
 - Purpose of the charter in relation to the author of the charter: According to your criteria, what is the purpose of the author of the document (e.g. to increase wealth, resolve a conflict, wealth management...).

4. Features of juridical action
 - The assembly where the judicial act is developed, is it an indicator of high social status?
 - In case of a transaction, is the subject of the contract an indicator of high social status?

- In case of a purchase, is it an indicator of high social status?
- The price (if it applies), is it set in coin?
- In case of a grant, is there any compensation?

5. Territory

- Is the territorial scale larger than a local frame?
- When the action is developed or involves different places (in the same or different territories), the action is considered superior to a local frame.

6. Social group associated with the individual: choose one of the following options, according to the closest social category to the individual or actor.

Diplomatic analysis

1. Documental tradition: is the text preserved as an original or a later copy?

2. Judicial action:

- According to the text: how does it define itself? It used to appear in the corroboration or date. For example: *kartula donationis*, *kartula vendicionis*, etc.
- According to the standard actual typology, the most approximated category.
 - Sale.
 - Will.
 - Grant.
 - Exchange.
 - Assets distribution agreement.
 - Agreement or dispute.
 - Charter of freedom.
- Observations: excluding the definition provided by the charter itself, what do you consider to be the real legal typology executed in this act?

3. Writing surface and uses:

- Parchment, but, is it a remnant?: A remnant or vestige may be from the neck of the animal, an armpit, or neither of them.

For example, this piece of parchment shows the back of the animal, but there are other documents written on pieces of parchment that correspond to the legs of animals, armpits, etc.

- Recto, but, flesh or hair? On which part of the parchment is the main text written?

➔ The flesh side is usually lighter, whereas the hair part is usually darker and small dots can be seen, which are the hair follicles of the animal.

The hair part

The flesh side

- Rectangular or square?
- Vertical or horizontal layout? Regarding the layout of the text.
- Opisthograph? Does it include documents on both sides?
- Ruling marks: Are there dry-point markings on the parchment to set the layout of the text and guide the writing?
- Pricking marks: Are there perforations to guide the ruled lines on the sides or holes in the corners to hold the document during writing?
- Tying tab: Is there any indication that there was a strip of the same parchment to tie the folded document?

- Other... Anything else you notice and want to highlight (moisture marks, marks from the writing process, etc.)?

4. Actuation phases

- The main text: Was it written at the same time or in different moments?
- Are there any dorsal annotations on the verso? These may be contemporary, written later, or both.

5. Internal features

- It includes a chrismon
- Type

Types of chrismons

Monogrammatic

Nuevo asturleonés from the 10th C.

Nuevo asturleonés simple (from the 11th C.)

Nuevo asturleonés double (from the 11th C.)

- Verbal invocation: Written invocation on behalf of the divinity (ex. *In Dei nomine*)
 - Graphic signs: Does it include confirmation signs, from the witnesses, subscribers, or/and the scribe?
6. Notes/observations: anything else you consider relevant regarding any other material or diplomatic aspects.

Graphic analysis

1. Scribe

- Name: The scribe's name as it appears on the document.
- Graphic training:
 - Elementary: the scribe is taking his first steps in writing or has not matured in writing (limited dexterity), has very basic or minimal skills. Letters that are not

fully formed, shaky and insecure strokes, usually slow, with practically no ligatures, but with hardly any syllabic separation of words. Almost no abbreviations are used. The arrangement of the support is irregular, with no respect for margins, the box of the line, alterations in the module or alterations in the ductus of the letters.

- Usual: the scribe is used to writing, has practice in writing. Has the graphic skills to write more fluently, with some ligatures and greater recursion. The scribe understands the graphic system, with an execution close to the canon, is familiar with the abbreviation system, however, it may present features of the most elementary level: in the structure, in the spelling, in the layout of the document, the line is not straight...
- Professional (in a non-formal setting): Shows an essential formation, as a result of frequent practice, despite they were not professionals. It shows a faster and safer execution, differentiated from the rest by its fluidity.

2. Typological / Graphic variant:

Mark with an x those elements that you observe in the document.

Visigothic cursive (VC)	
<p><i>c/e</i> with stroke to the left</p>	
<p>tall <i>u</i></p>	
<p>& for <i>-us/-um</i></p>	

Visigothic minuscule (VR)		
 <i>s</i> for <i>-us</i>		
 / for <i>-um</i>		

Caroline		
 <i>t</i> without eye		
 superscripted letters		
 <i>noster/uester</i> theme <i>r</i>		

Gothic script		
<p>Biting effect (between opposing curves)</p>	<p>Fracture: contrast between strokes</p>	

According to the observed elements, choose: a script, a degree of development and a degree of execution.

3. Degree of development

- Set or developed: It presents most of the characteristic forms of the graphic style.
- Evolved: with its own features, but its aspect is linked to the next graphic typology.

4. Type of script in accordance to the canon:

- Canonised: all features follow the same type
- Hybrid
 - Hybrid Visigothic Cursive: eminent presence of cursive but some feature of minuscule.
 - Hybrid Visigothic Minuscule: eminent presence of minuscule but some feature of cursive.
- Mixed
 - Visigothic-Caroline: Visigothic script, but some features from Caroline.
 - Caroline-Visigothic: Caroline with remains of Visigothic script.
 - Caroline-Gothic: Caroline with influences from Gothic script or any features.

5. Stroke speed:

- Slow:

- Fast:

Degree of execution

- Calligraphic: the shapes of the characters are according to the graphic model, with precise and uniform execution throughout the document.
- Rudimentary: the shapes of the letters are poorly defined according to the graphic model.
- Semicalligraphic / semirudimentary: the shapes of the characters are between the two previous ones.